

GENDER IDEOLOGICAL STANCES IN TRANSLATION AS INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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Abstract

Translation has always been a tool for broadening horizons, and for transferring knowledge from one culture to another. Over time and space, the intensity of translations has increased, and the quality and quantity of translated information has come along with a multitude of interlingual shifts. Admittedly, the topic of gender and translation “has been gaining critical consistency and experiencing a remarkable growth” (Castro 2013, 7). To put it crudely, translation is made up of words, but, linguistically, words can carry with them a certain ideological stance since language is an essential and influential medium of communication. In the translation of the discourse of advertising, as in many translation types, gender representation can be filtered by power and ideology, the gender bias being reinforced in several ways. In this context, the present paper focuses on the translation of advertisements, highlighting the translator’s ideological affiliation, alongside gender management strategies, within an interdisciplinary landscape, at the interface of translation studies, gender studies, sociolinguistics, critical discourse analysis and intercultural communication.

Keywords: translation, gender, ideology, culture, advertisements.

1. Introduction

In the last three decades, the focus has been on the impact that both language and translation have in transmitting the ideas, insights and cultures of certain peoples. Translation is considered to be one of the most suitable fields for studying ideological change and manipulation in language because it is not a neutral activity, as many scholars acknowledge (notably, Venuti 1995, 1998; Hatim and Mason 1997). Accordingly, translation is not just a process of transferring language symbols from one language to another but has become a process of rewriting a text interpreted by translators. As Das complains,

“translation has been treated more as a secondary activity than as a creative process, so it has a lower status” (Das 2008, 9). This low profile of translation has been long debated, and many voices, among which Lefevere’s (1992), seek to upgrade the translation role and function alongside the translator’s role. According to Bassnett (1980/1991, 15), the translator who takes a text and transposes it into another culture must carefully consider the ideological implications of this transposition; Baumgarten (2012, p.12) also promotes this idea when drawing attention to the fact that the ideological impact of translation has not been fully recognised in the past. Snell Hornby, (1990, 9-10) coins the phrase *cultural turn* to highlight the importance of cultural aspects in translation while Lefevere (1992, 12) goes even further when stating that “translation is, of course, a rewriting of an original text”. In this line of approach, translation shows the concern of solving issues that it shares with ideology, gender studies, sociolinguistics, critical discourse analysis and intercultural communication into another language. The study of translation does not only encompass various fields such as literary studies, sociolinguistics, discourse analysis, but it is also concerned with the transfer of information, opinions and cultural developments from one language to another. Through translation, a cross-cultural exchange of information takes place, influencing the readers’ feelings and emotions, sensations, thoughts, memories, perceptions, and it even manages to manipulate them in certain directions across their lives.

2. Gender and translation management strategies in an interdisciplinary landscape

More recently, the interplay between gender and translation has generated important work by various scholars, who are increasingly concerned with this area. To put it crudely, gender studies is an interdisciplinary academic discipline that investigates the issue of gender inequality, sexuality, masculinity, femininity and gender interaction as well as social processes of gender in relation to category, class and other elements of inequality systems (see Ayoun 2022).

Translation is defined as a “bilingually mediated communication” process (Neubert and Shreve 1992, 69) in which the translator should not be assimilated with the sender of the source text message, but with a text

producer in the target culture, adopting somebody else's intention "to produce a communicative instrument for the target culture, or a target-culture document of a source culture communication" (Nord 1991, 13).

The idea that "gender is a ubiquitous category in most social practices" (Lazar 2005, 3) is common in feminist linguistic research, as well as in feminist translation studies. In recent times, most scholarly work that encompasses these two areas of research highlights the role that both language and translation play in the context of the social world. In particular, the focus has been on investigating how gender roles are constructed through both language and translation, both of which are interpreted as proper social practices. All these gender representations are in continuous interaction with other factors such as race, category, geography, or sexuality, generating different implications at the level of material practice.

Language is an instrument of communication, of expressing ideas and feelings through language, which either perpetuates or challenges different structures existing in certain social and cultural contexts. Inevitably, both language and translation are a series of tools for upholding the *status quo*, or for gender liberation. From a gender perspective, the differential use of language by men and women is more than just a matter of linguistic forms; it is about the use of these forms in society and is ideologically constructed (Leonardi 2007, 38). The field of language is one of the effective and powerful tools of communication both in translations at a global level and in national processes and discourses. In the context of language being based on gender categories, the achievement of gender-neutral structures means to address the theorization of gender in many spheres of the language field. The linguistic sphere includes different research on the social change of language; while factors such as age, gender, class, ethnicity and region can be said to affect language use.

Language is a strategic tool of mediation and communication that either contributes to or combats existing power structures within socio-cultural contexts. The interplay between gender, language and translation creates new insights into how these are enhanced from cross-cultural and transnational perspectives on issues related to the study of linguistics but also to intercultural communication. Overall, language is

an important means of communication and its use lies in the very close connection it has with semantics and ideology, especially when we envisage cultural connotations.

In the context of the globalisation of culture and internationalisation of concepts, different companies collaborate with the help of translation, which is why it can be said that “we all live in translated worlds” (Simon 1996, 135). The obvious influence that different ideologies have on particular texts production and reception has been highlighted either directly or indirectly in search for an objective toolkit for interpreting and translating ideology (notably, Lefevere 1992, 217; Simon 1996, 218; Baker 2006, 221). Translation research has grown over time with the emergence of disciplines such as sociolinguistics and gender studies that examine the field of language within its infinite variability, as well as in terms of the correlation between human behaviour and perception. Therefore, translation is not only a process of transferring linguistic codes from one language to another, but it has also become a political activity (Li 2020) – in this context, translators have sought to eliminate difficulties in interpersonal communication in an age where language diversity is an integral part of people's lives.

The intersection between gender and translation has generated a whole literature, playing an important role in the analysis of the issues - thus, Flotow and Scott (2016, 78) use the term “transdiscipline” discussing the issues of translation and gender in relation to feminist translation, and women and translation. It can also be argued that gender translation makes this “transdiscipline” increasingly complex since translation “can be shown to be receptive to such manifestations of gender, [and to] accentuate them, or neglect obscure them” when it comes to intercultural and interlingual communication (Baker and Saldanha 2011, 124). It can be difficult to communicate gender-related ideas, attitudes, and ideologies, particularly if cultures are defensive or conservative towards them. Genderism is a challenging topic to tackle in translation research and practice since it is a culturally driven worldview.

Flotow (2019) enlarges upon two approaches to feminist translation. Within the first approach, translators innovate language and create feminist meanings underpinning deliberate textual manipulations. The second approach is premised by the idea that the

diversity of sexual and gender orientations, social classes, ethnic backgrounds, race, etc. is so wide that would be unwise or meaningless to work with the binary opposition male *versus* female. It is important to note that the term “feminism” emerged in the 19th century, originating in the French word “féminisme” perceived as a medical concept to define women with masculine characteristics. At the beginning of the 19th century, the feminist movement was called “feminism”. In the early twentieth century, in the United States, the term designated a particular type of women “namely that group which affirmed the uniqueness of women, the mystical experience of motherhood and the special purity of women” (Jaggar 1983, 5). Donovan (1992/2012, 12) also gives an overview of the history of feminism concluding that “feminists have reinvented the wheel a number of times”. Therefore, highlighting the connection that both translation, language and gender studies have makes us understand that the translator has a multitude of linguistic choices and s/he should be able to make the right decision, ideologically speaking.

3. Dealing with gender and ideology in the translation of advertisements

Advertising is envisaged a non-personal form of information, generally paid for, and persuasive in nature. Etymologically, the word “advertising” means “to bring out something” or “to inform” about something. Advertising can be used for several reasons: to motivate consumers to buy goods, or certain consumers not to buy goods, to change attitudes or to encourage retailers to stock products. For this reason, we encounter different advertising texts on different topics pertaining to the broad field of linguistics. The translation of advertising texts is one of the main methods of parallelism between the source text and the target text, highlighting advertising techniques as an integral part of a socio-cultural system. In other words, the concept of “advertising” is that form of communication designed to influence, inform and persuade the public about different products, services and activities. Language as an advertising tool deals with different themes, given the variety of possible areas of research.

As pointed above, an important aspect of the advertising discourse is the “art of persuasion”, the ability to manipulate the

audience through the use of language, which also plays an important role in informing people about certain consumer products. As far as responsibility in various translations is concerned, it is not limited to translators, as editors and readers also have a say. An important guideline in the (correct) translation of advertisements is represented by adaptation. In order to get the target text adapted, a translator needs to have full knowledge of the source text; this means that adaptation becomes an exclusive way to secure fitness for purpose, i.e., adjustment to the situation of the target culture (Nord 1994). Therefore, the translator aims to aim for the most effective translation in order to sell the advertised text as quickly as possible in the target culture; admittedly, the translators of advertisements have to take into account socio-cultural aspects of the target text such as religion, social customs and ethical standards.

Arens and Boveè, (1994, 271-272) endorse four basic rules that should be followed in the translation of advertisements:

- The translator must be an effective copywriter. The copywriter's goal is to attract attention, interest, desire, persuasion in relation to an advertisement. Copywriters use a set of techniques to generate the desired persuasive message: images, creative writing design, attractive colours. Design and layout can help the copywriter to give a stronger meaning to the words in the advertisement.

- The translator is required to understand the product characteristics and its market;

- Translators must be residents of the target country to ensure the correct use of idioms, cultural respect and social attitudes;

- The original text of the advertisement must be easy to translate.

The research on advertising discourse revealed that various gender stereotypes prevailing in a particular society are used to maximize advertising effectiveness. These gender stereotypes are regarded as pertinent since they are directly tied to gender roles, established by the culturally engrained specialization of male and female duties. Within the field of advertising, the specific nature of the functioning of stereotypes in the media context can be observed. Gender studies in media communication is an advanced research direction,

although it is not applied often enough. For instance, numerous scholars nowadays consider that TV advertising is designed to take into account gender groups, but also the translation of stereotypes to establish their importance in advertising. Two principles need to be emphasised with regard to the gender aspect of advertising. One is the generation of masculine and feminine forms of gender-sensitive advertising, another important strand is the translation of existing gender stereotypes in society used as a basis for advertising.

In advertising texts, adaptation as a translation method involves a cultural shift. In this context, the translator always has to constantly compare the source text and the target text, starting from an elaborate analysis of the intratextual (linguistic and structural) elements of the source text, which must be adapted to the extratextual elements of the target text. Usually, puns, jokes and jargon are very difficult to render because they are related to the specificity of a language. Advertisements convey a cultural message - the thoughts, ideas, concepts and beliefs of a country. Language is an expression of culture and the diversity of its speakers; therefore, the translator must first understand the meaning of the culture-specific elements of the source text and then translate these elements into the target text.

It is readily apparent that the language used in advertising is significantly distinct from the language used in daily life. It contains some features in terms of morphology, rhetorical techniques, and syntax, and it makes use of stylistic methods such figures of speech and others that are typically seen to be interesting to readers. Therefore, translators of advertisements, aiming to ensure that the advertisement is perceived by consumers in clear terms that cannot be misunderstood, have to use different signs that are appropriate to the culture in question. Thus, visual elements and language convey cultural symbols, and distinct symbolic links can be observed. Also, the visual elements in an advertisement carry across connotations as they describe how the user feels about a certain product. Translators of advertising materials need to know how to approach the semiotics of advertising materials. At the same time, the use of visual elements will allow the translator to use fewer (impactful) words. Let us examine the Coca-Cola claim - "always cool" (Fokam Kappe 2012: 50), "things go better with a Coke",

where the translators need to secure that the component elements of the multimodal message (image, language, sound) combine meaningfully and give the text its entirety, at the same time enabling the readership to understand the message in an unambiguous way.

Perhaps, the most important norms in the translation of advertisements are that the translator should not use lexical items that bear negative connotations, and that the translated text should comply with the user's ideology. The main objective for the translation of advertisements is for translators to consider advertisements as texts with a particular character, which have specific features and require translation functions as well as certain translation strategies. To put it crudely, we can state that the translator must be able to translate all the elements of the advertising material focusing on cultural symbols so that the translated text can be easily recognized by the readers/consumers.

4. Conclusions

This contextual triangle of the intersection of gender, language and translation is intended to create an interdisciplinary landscape, in which to leverage both the study of gender and translation as intercultural communication. Both gender studies and translation studies are connected in many specific ways such as: both are interdisciplinary fields that play an important role in many humanities. The interactions between gender, language, translation and intercultural communication offer new insights into how all of these are mediated from cross-cultural and transnational perspectives.

Advertising is an important field for most people as we encounter it every day, willingly or unwillingly. Moreover, advertising has developed significantly in recent times - it has turned into a huge industry where various brands advertise their different products. Advertising translation requires specific skills, and translation specialists should be aware of the advantage of translating their advertisements in order to reach a wider audience, because advertising translation is the means of communication *par excellence* of companies making their products available internationally. To mention only one specific challenge, advertising can be understood quite differently from one culture to another, therefore, it is necessary to use different

translation strategies and techniques, taking into account the cultural context of the target audience. It is also very important to understand how translators using visual and oral elements can translate different texts. We can point out that translators need to know how to transfer all the components of advertising texts into the target environment and must be able to focus on global cultural values in translating international advertising.

In conclusion, the translation of advertisements uses specific linguistic devices, and translators should possess linguistic and cultural knowledge and management strategies to ensure that the translation of the advertisement fits the situation of the target culture.

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